

www.arseam.com

AN ANALYSIS OF THE EMPLOYEE ATTRITION ISSUES AND RETENTION CHALLENGES IN ITES/BPO INDUSTRY - A PRAGMATIC STUDY

Mr. Jnaneshwar Pai Maroor

Ph.D (Management) Research Scholar
Centre for Research and Development
PRIST University
Vallam, Thanjavur,

Dr. B Vamana Baliga

Ph.D Research Supervisor,
PRIST University
Associate Professor ,
Commerce Department
Sri Mahaveera College, Moodbidri, India

ABSTRACT

These days, very often we come across the word “Attrition”. This word is being used in place of Employees turnover in an organization, used earlier. Attrition is the process of reducing the number of people who are employed by an organization by not replacing people who leave the job. Employee attrition refers to the loss of employees through a number of circumstances, such as resignation and retirement. The cause of attrition may be either voluntary or involuntary, though employer-initiated events such as layoffs are not typically included in the definition. Each industry has its own standards for acceptable attrition rates, and these rates can also differ between skilled and unskilled positions. Due to the expenses associated with training new employees, any type of employee attrition is typically seen to have a monetary cost. It is also possible for a company to use employee attrition to its benefit in some circumstances, such as relying on it to control labor costs without issuing mass layoffs. There are many different ways for a company to lose employees, most of which are typically taken into account to ensure that the organization is able to operate efficiently. Retirement is one major cause of employee attrition, and since people tend to retire around a specific age this is a factor that can be accounted and planned for. Other causes of employee attrition, such as personnel who quit due to prolonged illness, dissatisfaction with the company, or other reasons, can be more difficult to estimate. The study is also focused on retention challenges the company currently faces and to examine ways to reduce attrition rates among the employees working in the company.

Key words: Attrition, Retaining employees, Retention, Managers and organization

INTRODUCTION:

The percentage of employees that leave a company and terminated in a given period of time due to attrition is referred to as the attrition rate. A high attrition rate can adversely affect a company due to the costs of training new workers, though higher rates are often more acceptable for unskilled laborers than more highly skilled or trained workers. There are also circumstances where employee attrition can be used to benefit a company. In some circumstances, it becomes necessary for a company to cut labor costs to remain profitable. One method of dealing with this

type of issue is to lay off a number of workers but this can present more pressure of work for the existing employees. If the attrition rate is known, then simply not hiring new employees will result in fewer employees and savings in cost.

The cause of attrition may be either voluntary or involuntary. There are many different ways for a company to lose employees. Retirement is one major cause of employee attrition, and since people tend to retire around a specific age this is a factor that can be accounted and planned for.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Attrition is found to be making huge impact for any sectors like BPO's/ITES, because employee attrition represents significant costs to most organizations. The major problem faced by Diya systems is the increased employee attrition. This study is designed to address high employee attrition by identifying the nature and factors affecting attrition, analyzing level of employee motivation, satisfaction, and involvement in the company. The study is also focused on retention challenges the company currently faces and to examine ways to reduce attrition rates among the employees working in the company.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the employee perception about work environment, inter-personal relationship, occupational stress and growth & development.
- To identify and explore the dimensions of employee attrition in Diya systems based on the primary data collected from field survey.
- To identify and explore the dimensions of employee retention in Diya systems based on the primary data collected from field survey.
- To suggest innovative retention measures to reduce the attrition in Diya systems.

NEED FOR THE PRESENT STUDY

Most of the IT-BPO sectors are focusing only on the problems like challenges, growth and opportunities etc. No systematic study has been done on attrition, retention, employee

motivation, involvement, quality work life, career advancement etc to contend the problem of attrition. Attrition is main problem for all IT-BPO sectors because it fails to make use of the human resources and incurs huge cost in recruiting and training new employees. Lack of motivation among the employees is one also responsible for the attrition in IT-BPO sector. Therefore, need for the study is to tackle the problem of attrition in an effective manner by collecting the opinion from the employees of Diya systems regarding socio-economic features, work dimensions, attrition and retention dimensions and also to suggest innovative retention measures to the company to retain their skilled employees.

METHODOLOGY

The study was designed to understand the attrition in Diya systems. The primary data was collected by surveying employees of Diya systems using the structured questionnaire method. A sample size taken for this study constituted of 30 respondents. The respondent in the study included IT employees from low to mid-level. Simple random sampling has been used for data collection. The questionnaire consisted of 3 parts: Part 1 consisted of questions related to socio-economic features of employees and job features. Part 2 consisted of employees self evaluation, work dimensions such as work environment, inter-personal relationships, growth & development. Part 3 consisted of job satisfaction, factors affecting attrition of employees, and dimensions of retention measures of employees. The questionnaire was designed to obtain demographic variables including age, education, gender, marital status, tenure of the respondents and also gathered information about the factors responsible for attrition, measures adopted to retain the employees, employees overall level of satisfaction, motivation and involvement. The primary data were collected in the month of June 2014. SPSS version 14.0 was used for the statistical analysis. The secondary data is collected from websites, journals, books and newspapers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bean, J. P., & Metzner, B. S. (1985), Older, part-time, and commuter students have composed an increasingly larger portion of college student bodies. The reasons why these students drop out of school are not well understood. The purpose of this paper is to describe the rise in nontraditional enrollments, define the nontraditional undergraduate student, and develop a

conceptual model of the attrition process for these students. The chief difference between the attrition process of traditional and nontraditional students is that nontraditional students are more affected by the external environment than by the social integration variables affecting traditional student attrition.

Sengupta, S., & Gupta, A. (2012), says that Business process outsourcing (BPO) industry in India is progressing with an unparalleled velocity. Despite the momentous growth and brilliant future, the BPO industry has experienced high attrition rates since inception. There are many factors that lead to attrition in BPOs and much research has taken place time and again. In this study, they made a comprehensive attempt to explore the dimensions of attrition by identifying the factors that lead to it, assessing the contribution of the factors toward attrition, and comparing the dimensions across the various demographic variables.

Srivastav, A. K. (2010), coded that how organizational climate operates in BPO industry. Six motives of organizational climate were measured in BPO companies. Expert Influence and Extension were respectively the dominant and backup climates. Affiliation was the weakest climate. Exploratory factor analysis of climate motives revealed three meta-climates operating in BPO industry: (1) Brazen Shirking combining heightened Dependency and de-emphasized Affiliation, (2) Empowered Collaboration representing heightened Extension and de-emphasized Control, (3) Obsession for Expertise combining heightened Expert Influence and de-emphasized Achievement. 70.30% variance explains these meta-climates that reflect the realities in BPO industry.

Chandrasekar, K. (2011), says that Human Resource is considered to be the most valuable asset in an Organization. It continues to play, even in the computer age, when everybody feels that men have a little role to play. It is true that computer, to some extent, does play a role, but programming and feeding such programme require manual operations. In other words, the application of manpower has no substitute and therefore, it has a continuous role to play. The main problem against the manpower development is attrition. The rate of attrition is increasing every day so that production and profit decrease. Noteworthy is the continuously growing rate of attrition among the IT, ITES and other Software based companies. This has made the companies to take up research studies based on their employees, especially to identify the factors of attrition. This research helps to know about the employees' attitude towards the company and the

work, also highlighting various other direct and indirect effects of attrition on production, cost, discipline and efficiency in the industry.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data analysis involves analysis of the summarized data. Summarized data is obtained by tabulating the collected data and thereby processing it to give a summarized output.

Cross tabulation: Gender * Reason for joining Diya systems

		Reason for joining Diya systems				Total
		Good Salary	Good work environment	Job content	Bright career prospects	
Gender	Male	3	4	1	11	19
	Female	1	5	0	5	11
Total		4	9	1	16	30

Interpretation: From the above cross tabulation Table it is observed that the reason for joining Diya systems by male employees is more because of bright career prospects. Out of 19 males only 1 employee looked at job content. The female employees joined Diya systems because of good work environment and bright career prospects and only one female employee looked at good salary. And total we can see that employees mostly prefer Diya systems because of bright career prospects.

Frequency table

Work Experience of employees in Diya systems

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Below 1 year	1	3.3	3.3	3.3
	1-2 years	4	13.3	13.3	16.7
	3-5 years	15	50.0	50.0	66.7
	Above 5 years	10	33.3	33.3	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The above Table shows that majority of the data collected by the employees who are experienced between 3-5 years. Out of 30 employees 1 employee is experienced below one year, 4 employees experienced between 1-2 years, 15 employees experienced between 3-5 years and 10 employees experienced above 5 years. That means data through questionnaire are collected from the employees who are highly experienced. They have given opinion on employee attrition and retention in Diya systems.

Nature of Service rendered by Diya systems

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Administration	9	30.0	30.0	30.0
	Customer relationship	12	40.0	40.0	70.0
	Content development	9	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: According to the table shown above, most of the employees agree that Diya Systems is giving more importance to customer relationship and next administration and content development. As per the analysis it is found that the company is not providing health care facilities to employees.

Work time or shifts in Diya systems

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Day shift	23	76.7	76.7	76.7
	Day-night shift	7	23.3	23.3	100.0
	Total	30	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Above table depicts that 23 employee's work for day shift, only 7 employee's work for day-night shift and no employee's work for night shift which also means 76.7% of the employee's work for day shift whereas 23.3% of employee's work for day-night shift.

FACTOR ANALYSIS**Factor analysis for Employee's self evaluation on their skills****1. KMO and Bartlett's Test**

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.703
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	154.233
	Df	28
	Sig.	.000

Interpretation: The KMO test measures the sampling adequacy which should be greater than 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Bartlett's test is another indication of the strength of the relationship among variables. In the above table, the value of KMO is 0.703 and Bartlett's test shows significant results, which implies factor analysis is a feasible study.

2. Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
Good command over English speaking	1.000	.856
Computer literacy	1.000	.588
Knowledge of customer	1.000	.792
Responding skills	1.000	.736
Analytical skills	1.000	.802
Phone etiquette	1.000	.832
Listening skills	1.000	.750
Adaptability skills	1.000	.741

Interpretation: The table above shows the extraction of the employee's self-evaluation data on their skills. The initial Eigen value is 1.00 for all the variables. According to the communalities, it is clear that variable good command over English, phone etiquette and analytical skills has got higher extraction value of 0.856, 0.832 and .802. The variable computer literacy has got less extraction value of 0.588.

3. Total Variance Explained

SI N o	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.41	55.174	55.174	4.41	55.174	55.174	3.33	41.684	41.684
2	1.68	21.041	76.215	1.68	21.041	76.215	2.76	34.531	76.215
3	.555	6.943	83.158						
4	.445	5.564	88.722						
5	.380	4.748	93.471						
6	.308	3.852	97.322						
7	.129	1.615	98.937						
8	.085	1.063	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Interpretation: From the table shown above, in the first section two factors emerged accounting for 76.215% of the variance. Only two factors in the initial solution have Eigen values greater than 1. Eigen values greater than 1 are considered and rest is treated as irrelevant. In the second section and third section of the table, Extracted sum of squared loadings and rotated sum of squared loadings are presented where two factors emerged also accounts for 76.215%. Varimax rotation is used.

4. Rotated Component Matrix

	Factor	
	1	2
Good command over English speaking	.916	
Computer literacy		
Knowledge of customer		.889
Responding skills		.828
Analytical skills		.872
Phone etiquette	.912	
Listening skills	.816	
Adaptability skills	.779	
	Communication Skills	Customer Orientation

Interpretation: In the rotated component matrix, factor loading greater than 0.6 are considered. The Table shows that factor loading for each of the variables on the two factors that have

emerged. Communication skills are named as factor 1 and customer orientation is named as factor 2.

Factor analysis for work culture dimensions

1. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.571
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	389.807
	Df	171
	Sig.	.000

In the above table, the value of KMO is 0.571 and Bartlett’s test shows significant results, which means that factor analysis is feasible for the study.

2. Communalities

Communalities show the extraction of the work culture dimensions data. From the analysis done it is clear that variables such as opportunity for using skills and abilities, superior-subordinate relationship and opportunity for challenging work has got higher extraction value of 0.920, 0.913 and 0.883. The variable insufficient break has got less extraction value of 0.703.

3. Total Variance Explained

From the analysis done, in the first section six factors emerged accounting for 81.315% of the variance. In the second section and third section, extracted sum of squared loadings and rotated sum of squared loadings are presented where two factors emerged also accounts for 81.315%.

4. Rotated Component Matrix

	Factor					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Risk and Uncertainty		.756				
Roles and responsibilities						
Temperature lighting and ventilation		.883				
Personal health and safety		.838				

Mental and emotion well being						.875
Team work			.782			
Colleagues cooperation			.844			
Superior subordinate relationship					.775	
Roles of HRD					.793	
High work pressure				.840		
Insufficient breaks						
Physical strain						
Irritating customers				.829		
Repetitive nature of work						
Opportunity for promotion						
Opportunity to shift career line	.644	.607				
Opportunity for growth and security	.848					
Opportunity for challenging work	.916					
Opportunity for using skills and abilities	.910					
	Good career prospects	Work Environment	Interpersonal relationship	Work Stress	Intra-Organizational Relationship	Mental & emotional well being

Interpretation: In the rotated component matrix, factor loading greater than 0.6 are considered. The Table shows the factor loading for each of the variables on the two factors that have emerged. Good career prospects are named as factor 1, work environment is named as factor 2, Inter-personal relationship is named as factor 3, Work stress is named as factor 4, organizational relationship is named as factor 5 and mental and emotional well being is named as factor 6.

Factor analysis for Job satisfaction**1. KMO and Bartlett's Test**

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.646
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	91.031
	Df	21
	Sig.	.000

In the above table, the value of KMO is 0.646 and Bartlett's test shows significant results, which means that factor analysis can be carried out for the study.

2. Communalities

Communalities show the extraction of the job satisfaction data. The initial Eigenvalue is 1.00 for all the variables. From the analysis done it is clear that work culture has got higher extraction value of 0.835. The variable like work environment and job rotation has got less extraction value of 0.570 and 0.547.

3. Total Variance Explained

From the analysis done, in the first section two factors emerged accounting for 68.853% of the variance. In the second section and third section, extracted sum of squared loadings and rotated sum of squared loadings are presented where two factors emerged also accounts for 68.853%.

4. Rotated Component Matrix (a)

	Factor	
	1	2
Nature of work		.798
Job description		.817
Work environment	.676	
Work culture	.914	
Job rotation		.740
Freedom to decide and suggest	.721	
	Open culture	Learning environment

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

In the rotated component matrix, factor loading greater than 0.6 are considered. The Table shows the factor loading for each of the variables on the two factors that have emerged. Open culture are named as factor 1 and learning environment is named as factor 2.

Factor analysis for attrition dimensions

1. KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.523
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	510.943
	Df	210
	Sig.	.000

In the above table, the value of KMO is 0.523 and Bartlett's test shows significant results, which means that factor analysis may be useful with data and accepted for the study.

2. Communalities

Communalities show the extraction of the factors affecting attrition data. The variable lack of advancement opportunities has got higher extraction value of 0.906. The variable such as low perceived value, personal reasons, incompatible policies, dissatisfied with colleagues and poor mentoring has got next highest extraction value of 0.859, 0.846, 0.830, 0.823, and 0.807. The variables such as ineffective supervision, lack of autonomy, emphasis on quality over quantity, dissatisfied with working conditions and absence of challenge has got lesser extraction of 0.685, 0.677, 0.658, 0.642 and 0.609.

3. Total Variance Explained

From the analysis done, in the first section five factors emerged accounting for 75.893% of the variance. In the second section and third section, extracted sum of squared loadings and rotated sum of squared loadings are presented where five factors emerged also accounts for 75.893%.

In the rotated component matrix, factor loading greater than 0.6 are considered. The Table shows the factor loading for each of the variables on the two factors that have emerged. HRM issues is named as factor 1, career prospects is named as factor 2, compatibility issues is named as factor 3, no recognition is named as factor 4 and personal reasons is named as factor 5.

4. Rotated Component Matrix

	Factor				
	1	2	3	4	5
Personal reasons					.892
Lack of advancement opportunities					
Lack of skill variety		.738			
Dearth of self motivation					
Low perceived value		.840			
Monotonous nature of job		.687			
Lack of equality					
Dissatisfied with compensation					
Incompatible policies			.845		
Absence of challenge	.633				
Irregular working hours	.684				
Power and politics	.764				
Poor mentoring	.625				
Dissatisfied with colleagues	.864				
Emphasis on quantity over quality	.789				
Lack of team work	.835				
Ineffective supervision	.780				
Dissatisfied with working conditions	.728				
Unsure of career growth		.800			
Achievement not recognized				.777	
Lack of autonomy	.760				
	HRM issues	Career prospects	Compatibility issues	No recognition	Personal reasons

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Factor analysis for retention factors**1. KMO and Bartlett's Test**

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		.526
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	366.754
	Df	171
	Sig.	.000

In the above table, the value of KMO is 0.526 and Bartlett's test shows significant results, which means that factor analysis may be useful with data and accepted for the study.

2. Communalities

Communalities show the extraction of the retention measures data. According to the communalities, it is clear that variables such as opportunity to help other people, feeling of self esteem, sense of accountability for employee’s job position, feeling of self fulfillment has got higher extraction value of 0.876, 0.852, 0.843 and 0.817. The variables such as opportunity to move ahead in life, feeling of worthwhile accomplishment and housing conveyance medical benefits has got less extraction value of 0.594, 0.570,0.540.

3. Total Variance Explained

From the analysis done, in the first section five factors emerged accounting for 71.978% of the variance. In the second section and third section of the table, extracted sum of squared loadings and rotated sum of squared loadings are presented where five factors emerged also accounts for 71.978%.

4. Rotated Component Matrix

	Factor				
	1	2	3	4	5
Feeling of self esteem				.915	
Housing Conveyance Medical benefits					
Salary offered			.818		
Opportunity for personal growth and development			.791		
Opportunity to develop close friendship					.825
Authority connected with employees position	.605				
Opportunity to help other people	.774				
Facilities provided for effective working					
Feeling of self fulfillment				.770	
Employees overall involvement in work	.684				
Employees role at job position		.795			
Sense of accountability for employees job position		.899			
Prestige of employees job position inside Organization		.605			

Opportunity for independent thought and action	.712				
Security of employees job position				.667	
Feeling of worthwhile accomplishment	.713				
Participation in determination of methods and procedures	.700				
Opportunity to move ahead in life and become well known					
Prestige of employees job position outside Organization					
	Employee freedom	Good Employee morale	Monetary benefits & personal Growth	Good feelings about employees	Close networking

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

In the rotated component matrix, factor loading greater than 0.6 are considered. The Table shows the factor loading for each of the variables on the two factors that have emerged. Employee freedom is named as factor, good employee morale is named as factor 2, monetary benefits & personal growth is named as factor 3, good feeling about employees is named as factor 4 and close networking is named as factor 5.

Interpretation

Based on employee perceptions a model is been developed in employee attrition and retention. This model makes an attempt to connect the factors of attrition and factors for retention in Diya systems with the factors on work culture dimensions, employee’s skills and job satisfaction. In the above model we find that HRM issues are mostly connected with interpersonal relationship, intra-organizational relationship and mental & emotional well being. Poor career prospects are connected with communication skills, customer orientation and learning environment. Compatibility issues are connected with work environment and open culture. Personal reasons are connected with work stress. Employee freedom is connected with good career prospects, work environment and open culture. Monetary benefits & personal growth is connected with intra-organizational relationship, communication skills and customer orientation.

Good feeling about employees is connected with open culture. Close network is connected with inter-personal relationship and intra-organizational relationship.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Provide maximum opportunities for existing employees to develop their skills and move on their careers.
2. Provide an opportunity for employees to voice their opinion on the changes that is going to take place in Diya systems.
3. Provide fair salary, increase in pay regularly and other monetary benefits according to the employee's ability and performance.
4. Employees should be allowed to work freely at work place and there should not be any interruption again and again by the senior managers.
5. Don't make employees work for overtime because work becomes inefficient.
6. Don't make employees work on repetitive nature of work; instead include them in all kinds of work.
7. Appreciate and reward employees for their contributions according to their performance. This will make employees get motivated to work better.
8. Employee satisfaction, motivation, involvement, recognition and morale are more important thus improve all these steps to retain employees.
9. Managers should be loyal and friendly with their employees so train managers in such a way to treat employees with

CONCLUSION

According to the study analyzed on the topic "Consultative study of attrition & retention in diya systems", it is identified that some attrition factors are emerged like HRM issues, poor career prospects, compatibility issues, no employee recognition and employee personal reasons. Among these, major ones are HRM issues and poor career prospects. Therefore, we conclude that diya systems should consider these causes and take several innovative retention steps to reduce attrition in their company. By doing this, employees will get motivated themselves and will increase their attitude towards company to remain for a longer period.

References

- Chandrasekar, K. (2011). Managing Attrition: The Real Problem Behind the Growth of Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) Companies. *Journal of Social Welfare & Management*, 3.
- Sengupta, S., & Gupta, A. (2012). Exploring the dimensions of attrition in Indian BPOs. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 23(6), 1259-1288.
- Raman, R. (2006). Strategies to retain human capital in Business Process Outsourcing (BPO) industry. Kohinoor Business School, Khandala, Working Paper.
- Srivastav, A. K. (2010). Organizational Climate: BPO Industry. *SCMS Journal of Indian Management*, 7(2).
- Vibha Gupta- “*An analysis of attrition : Retention strategy for IT/BPO Industry*”, *International Journal of Advanced research in Computer science and Management Studies*, volume 1, issue 7, ISSN: 2321-7782, (2013)
- Athul Marthur, P. K. Agarwal- “*A study on impact of Employee retention in Private Sector*”, *International journal of emerging research in management and technology*, ISSN: 2278-9359, (2013)
- Shivangee Singh, Pankaj Kant Dixit- “*Employee Involvement: An approach to Organizational development and change*”, *VSRD International journal of business & management research*, volume 1(8),554-560 (2011)
- “*Retaining your best people*”- The results driven manager series, ISBN 1-59139-973-4, Harvard business school press (2009).
- “*Motivating people for improved performance*”- The results driven manager series, ISBN 1-59139-779-0, Harvard business school press (2009)